

The virus is a microscopic infectious agent that is considered non living outside the host cell, and inside the host cell, it reproduces, generally consisting of a genetic material, a protein coat, and, in some cases, a lipid envelope. Though its microscopic agent has been threatening mankind for centuries as it possesses immense potential as well as the risk of new viral outbreaks has grown rapidly.

When a virus invades the human body, normally white blood cells and other phagocytes attack the virus and consume it. If the host body has already been vaccinated against a certain virus, the immune system can easily identify it, which initiates an immune response against this specific strain of virus. As viruses are muted rapidly, which we noticed in COVID-19, for that reason, the past vaccine may not be able to give the immune response, and this is exactly what happened in COVID-19. Viruses have different types. One is the RNA virus, which has a specialty to mutate at a much higher rate compared to others, which enhances its transmissibility and changes its binding site, virulence, and resistance to the immune system and also immune direction. But all mutants are not dangerous for humans; they may also benefit human life. For example, in many vaccines, mutated virus strains are used, so it is difficult to predict which virus will cause the disease and the next pandemic. Under the right conditions, some viruses can be to humans from Avian; not only that, many viruses can exchange their genetic material with other viruses. H1N1 swine flu is one of those kinds. (Holmes,2022) RNA viruses like influenza mutated so fast that there is a necessity for the development of a new flu vaccine every year. (Itpartners, 2023) Maximum RNA viruses cannot do proofreading. For that reason, the possibility of mutation increases whenever they are multiplying. This ability has both good sides and bad sides. The good side is some mutations may reduce the capabilities of the causing disease, and the bad side is they can also increase the lethality. Though most of the mutations are minor and don't affect the virus's transmission rate and the severity of the disease, in some cases, it can be difficult to treat the disease. In influenza viruses, genetic mutations happen, which are responsible for its antigens to "drift"— meaning the surface of the mutated virus looks different than the original virus when it drifts enough, the vaccine would work against the

new strain thus, the host cell will be affected by the Influenza. (How Do Viruses Mutate and What It Means for a Vaccine? | Pfizer, n.d.)

Reference

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